

DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL MODELS TO INCREASE STUDENTS' INTEREST IN SCIENCE IN SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article provides instructions on the development of modern models in the specialized schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan to increase students' interest in science and increase the knowledge and potential of students. Based on this, in-depth lessons are organized based on the interests of students. For example, a group of students wants to have more knowledge in mathematics, because they are tested on mathematics in the process of applying to higher education institutions. In specialized schools, teachers can ensure the quality of lesson processes using modern teaching models. Based on modern educational models, students' interest in this subject increases. In order for students to actively participate in the lesson process, holding question-and-answer contests or interesting games during the lesson will ensure that students will have memorable information. In this case, the teacher forms a method based on his pedagogical potential and knowledge.

Keywords: Specialized schools, modern educational, educational models, pedagogical skills, specialized pedagogues, quality of education.

Introduction

To date, strategic models for the development of modern educational models have been developed in specialized schools in the Republic of Karakalpakstan to increase students' interest in science. The main goal and task of these educational models is to improve the quality of education in specialized schools and to create modern educational methods. A teaching method is required from the teacher to increase the interest of schoolchildren in subjects and to improve the quality of education. The teacher should develop methodological methods for each of the specified topics. Science should be based on accurate data and analysis in a systematic way, explained clearly and simply. When implementing

strategies for creating an educational program based on modern models, it is necessary to form school rating indicators based on the criteria for evaluating education in specialized schools. In the process of explaining the topic, the teacher should form a method of explaining to the students through information technologies, computer graphics, internet data, books and video data. It is necessary to attract qualified personnel in the system of teaching basic subjects to students. The teacher must have pedagogical skills, competence and knowledge. The main goal of the program is to attract qualified teachers to basic subjects, so that after graduating from specialized schools, they will transfer to higher education. Admission to higher education is conducted in test mode. Students are admitted to higher education based on test results in basic subjects. For this, teachers are recommended to use modern models of education to provide quality education to students. Forming a program for the development of modern models of education in specialized schools in the Republic of Uzbekistan, using modern technologically equipped rooms, laboratory rooms, libraries, and electronic textbooks for students to carry out chemical laboratory training computer rooms should be organized for. Specialized pedagogues in the Republic of Uzbekistan have many experiences of the reform of the development of modern models of education in increasing students' interest in science. The intended purpose of this educational research is that we can learn the content and essence of the models used to improve the quality of education in specialized schools. One of the main tasks is to achieve high results of students in mastering subjects in schools based on modern models of education. Chemistry teacher Jumamuratov R. has been reflecting on the program of development of educational models in schools in his research. Many of his articles on the modern methodology of teaching chemistry in schools have been published in scientific and international journals. In organizing these methods, based on modern educational models, every school teacher can create new methods in his subject. Qualified pedagogue chemistry teacher Jumamuratov.R. has conducted many studies on the formation of chemistry teaching methodology in schools. The main content and essence of these studies is to create methods on a simple, understandable topic for students in school education. The object of pedagogy is mainly schoolchildren, and the subject is the theory of education given to students and practice. Pedagogy meets the needs of society and the purpose of education learning content depending on the age characteristics of the students requires going, the components of education and they reveals the connections between At the same time, education and

upbringing summarizes experiences in the field, the future of education shows the prospects and ways of development. Turemuratova A., an assistant teacher at the department of pedagogy and psychology at the Karakalpak State University, has been carrying out many studies on the formation of modern methods in the educational process and the enrichment of students' outlook. His researches based on pedagogical and psychological experiences in pedagogy and modern education have been published in many international scientific journals. Pedagogical skills are all forms of the educational process organization in the most convenient and efficient way, their personal development orientation towards goals, formation of students' (pupils') outlook, abilities, necessary for society is to arouse a tendency to activity. Knowing the uniqueness of the pedagogical goal in the following can:

1. The purpose of pedagogical activity is determined by society, that is, the result of the pedagogue's activity is in the interests of society depends. His work matured the personality of young people in every way aimed at finding. Pedagogical activity is social of the generation provides continuity (sequence). The experience of one generation, the second it is natural in humans to acquire social experience realizes the possibility.

2. Pedagogical activity is always with personal activity management depends. In this case, the pedagogical goal becomes the student's goal is important. The goal of the teacher's activity and its achievement students to clearly imagine the ways and achieve this goal it is necessary to be able to tell them that it is important for them.

The effect of any lesson is its result, i.e. students is measured by the level of formed knowledge, skills and qualifications, but this result largely depends on the person-teacher depends on preparation. The thorough preparation of the teacher who went to the class is the basis of education ensures its effectiveness, so before entering the class the teacher is thoroughly trained both psychologically and scientifically must see. Psychological preparation means the following. The lesson is a complex process, in which various mental features; character, willpower, memory, attention, participation of students with thinking and temperament enough. During the lesson, one of the above-mentioned features is shown by students in one way. Moreover, in every moment of the lesson, no one can plan in advance situations arise. However, the teacher is mentally different solve the problem in the right way without losing yourself in any situation should be ready to solve. For this, every teacher to imagine the environment of the future lesson and prepare oneself for it should be prepared.

Preparation in science means the following. Before organizing the lesson, the teacher has his subject in the designated class considering which subject should be passed from the curriculum takes then to the State educational standards on this topic addressing and determining what to educate students about takes Existing textbooks or literature, as well as visual or how well other educational tools meet the requirements of the curriculum opportunities to help illuminate the topic by determining what it gives will know. Getting acquainted with the educational material described in the textbook, today's tasks and the knowledge of students adapts to the level, and if necessary, makes changes and corrections. The development of interactive, collaborative and dynamic e-learning methods is under consideration it is necessary to choose the main method of evolution of international education systems in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Most of the studies. Revealed the widespread advantages of these technologies and showed their applications and their examples we will be able to learn the stages of evolution in the educational system. However, few studies clearly define the role of e-learning platforms to improve education and how these technologies can be integrated information is provided in the classroom. A new approach to the integration of these systems in the school education system is proposed from identifying and understanding the emotions of teachers, providing educational acts in relation to this type of innovative technology, it is necessary to explain and interpret the results of qualitative research. Teacher's perception of the role of e-learning is interpreted as a factor affecting the quality of use and integration of these technologies. The educational environment in the schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan once again confirms the need for consistent implementation of these tools not only at the level of a specific school, but also in the integration of the general educational environment. Recently, virtual learning systems supported by computer learning often try to reinforce authoritarianism. The role of the virtual learning method in educational systems is considered to be the transfer of knowledge based on subsequent methods based on computer-assisted cooperative learning it is necessary to develop knowledge sharing. In modern education, many technologies can be used in e-learning, options range from blogs to collaboration software, e-portfolios and virtual classrooms. In many cases when using e-learning, or rather, when using new technologies in education, a combination of these methods is used. In addition, the use of virtual classrooms online is increasing A training platform should be implemented for various training service providers. Except for the virtual environment classrooms, social networks have become an important part

of electronic education. Social networks are used a program to promote an online learning community on a variety of topics, such as test or study preparation. Although these schools did not respond to trends, most teachers rejected traditional social attitudes network in education if communication can manage communication between them and their colleagues.

Conclusion

In short, a lot of information has been given on the development of modern models of education to increase students' interest in science in specialized schools. In this, pedagogues should create simple and understandable methods for each subject. In the method, it is necessary to use interesting, accurate, necessary information about science and the topic. For this, pedagogical skills and potential are required from teachers. The teacher should pay attention to the students during the lesson. For this, it is necessary to use methodologies based on interesting and quality education.

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